

IMPACT CHARACTERISTICS OF SHEET MOLDING COMPOUND WITH DIFFERENT TAPE MORPHOLOGY AND EFFECT OF CONTINUOUS CFRTP OVER-MOLDING

Sang Won Lim¹, Fan Zhang¹, Yi Wan¹ and Jun Takahashi¹

¹Department of Systems Innovation, Graduate School of Engineering, The University of Tokyo
Hongo 7-3-1, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo, Japan
Email: swlim@g.ecc.u-tokyo.ac.jp

Keywords: Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics, Sheet molding compound, Hybrid composites, Impact properties, Finite element analysis

ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic sheet molding compound (CFRTP-SMC) presents a promising alternative to the conventional continuous fiber composites due to its superior formability, in-plane isotropy, high production efficiency, and recyclability, particularly through the reutilization of end-of-life waste and prepreg scrap. In automotive applications, where environmental regulations and large-scale production are critical, CFRTP-SMC is increasingly investigated for its potential in future mobility. However, there are concerns regarding adoption of discontinuous based composite for structural members of an automobile where high energy absorption is required to ensure the safety of passengers. This study examines the impact behavior of CFRTP-SMC under three-point bending, along with a hybrid unidirectional (UD) carbon fiber over-molded CFRTP-SMC variant. Different tape lengths are investigated to identify the critical tape length for enhanced energy absorption and impact strength. Additionally, the influence of UD carbon fiber over-molding on impact performance is assessed. A multi-scale microstructural model analysis is conducted to estimate the material's engineering constants for experimental-analytical correlation using finite element methods. Results indicate that the critical tape length identified significantly increase the impact performance of CFRTP-SMC, and further improvements in energy absorption can be achieved through the utilization of UD carbon fiber over-molding without compromising weight reduction objectives.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) are widely employed in engineering applications due to their high specific strength and stiffness. In particular, discontinuous-carbon fiber reinforced plastics have gained attention in automotive sectors for their superior formability and production efficiency – key considerations in mass production. In addition, more progressive and demanding environmental regulations targeting carbon emission reduction has accelerated interest in thermoplastic-based CFRP, which offer notable advantages in recyclability [1-3]. However, the use of discontinuous thermoplastic composites in structural members of automobiles remains limited due to concerns over their impact performance, which is critical for passenger protection.

In response, recent research has focused on discontinuous composites reinforced with long carbon fibers, such as carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic sheet molding compounds (CFRTP-SMC). CFRTP-SMC is a type of SMC consisting of carbon fiber reinforcements in the form of tapes or tows with a thermoplastic resin, offering advantages in forming complex shapes, cost-effectiveness for large-scale production, and excellent mechanical properties. The bundled morphology of the carbon fibers in CFRTP-SMC results in superior mechanical performance compared to the conventional injection-molded composites while maintaining quasi-isotropic behavior. Building on these advantages, Takahashi and Wan developed methods for fabricating quasi-isotropic SMC using randomly distributed carbon fiber prepreg tapes [4]. They analyzed the influence of tape length on mechanical performance through X-ray micro-computed tomography scanning with estimations using Monte Carlo stochastic simulation [5]. Similarly, Alves et al. examined the properties of quasi-isotropic tow-based SMC [6, 7], while Katsivalis et al. extended this work by developing predictive models for failure behavior [8].

While the static mechanical properties of SMC have been extensively studied, the influence of tape length on their impact performance remains largely unexplored. Furthermore, the potential of hybridizing SMC with unidirectional (UD) carbon fiber through over-molding has not yet been systematically investigated. In this paper, the critical tape morphology that saturates the impact properties of CFRTP-SMC is assessed. In addition, the effect of UD carbon fiber over-molding on enhancing impact characteristics is examined.

The proposed framework highlights the influence of tape morphology on the impact performance of CFRTP-SMC, as well as effective utilization of UD reinforcements without compromising weight reduction goals. These results emphasize the strong potential of CFRTP-SMC and its hybrid variants for structural applications in the automotive industry, particularly in the context of large-scale and sustainable manufacturing.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Molding and specimen preparation

This study investigates CFRTP-SMC with two distinct tape lengths, alongside a hybrid variant combining CFRTP-SMC with UD reinforcement. The SMC preform sheets were manufactured by randomly distributing chopped prepreg tapes consisting of carbon fiber (TR50S, Mitsubishi Chemical Co.) and polyamide-6 resin (PA6, DIAMIRON™ C, Mitsubishi Chemical Co.). The SMC preform was stacked with approximately 95-100 grams of pure SMC sheets, where its hybrid variant was stacked with 85-90 grams of SMC sheets and a single layer of UD ply on one side of the outermost surface so that the total material weight remained equivalent. Figure 1 and Table 1 provide details of the material configurations and their respective designations. SMC_10 and SMC_30 refer to SMC plates reinforced with 10 mm and 30 mm tapes, respectively. Hybrid_L and Hybrid_U denote SMC plates with 30 mm tapes, further reinforced with a single layer of UD carbon fiber layer on the lower and upper surfaces, respectively.

Figure 1: Material representation: (a) SMC 10 mm tapes, (b) SMC 30 mm tapes, (c) UD carbon fiber

Material type	Tape length SMC [mm]	No. SMC plies	No. UD plies	Total weight [g]
SMC_10	10	8	0	95-100
SMC_30	30	8	0	95-100
Hybrid_L	30	7	1 lower layer	95-100
Hybrid_U	30	7	1 upper layer	95-100

Table 1: Material identification.

The preformed sheets were then compression-molded into panels measuring 250 x 125 mm with a nominal thickness of 2.0 mm. Both the SMC and hybrid panels were molded under identical conditions using a press machine (265 °C, 50 bars, 25 mins) with the carbon fiber volume fraction of 50% to ensure direct comparability. The molded panels were subsequently sectioned into 120 x 60 mm specimens using a composite material cutting machine (MARUTO Testing Machine Company, AC-500CF), as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematics of mold cavity, plate, and specimen geometry

2.2 Impact experiment

Three-point bending impact tests on the materials listed in Table 1 were conducted with a high-speed impact testing machine (Hydroshot HITS-P10, Shimadzu Corporation) under the JIS K7084 standards with three different impact velocities. The sample dimensions and testing conditions are detailed in Table 2. To evaluate the impact properties, a minimum of five samples were prepared for each condition. The maximum impact stress, σ_{max} and the specific energy absorption, SEA are calculated using equations (1) and (2). The force, F and work W are measured from the testing machine, while the dimensions L , w , and t represent the gauge length, width, and thickness, respectively. The variable m denotes the mass of the specimen.

Dimensions			No. of specimens	Impact velocity [m/s]
Gauge length	Width	Thickness		
[mm]	[mm]	[mm]		
80	60	2	> 5	1.5, 2.0, 2.5

Table 2: Sample dimensions and testing conditions for the three-point bending impact experiment.

$$\sigma_{max} = \frac{3FL}{2wt^2} \quad (1)$$

$$SEA = \frac{W}{m} \quad (2)$$

2.3 Multi-scale modelling

The theoretical material properties and associated engineering constants for both SMC and UD materials were estimated using Digimat-MF (Hexagon AB), a multi-scale modelling platform based on mean-field homogenization theory for composites behavior prediction. The raw material properties of carbon fiber (Young's modulus: 230 GPa) and Polyamide-6 (Young's modulus: 3 GPa) were used as input parameters to estimate the composite properties. The twelve engineering constants include Young's moduli (E_{xx} , E_{yy} , E_{zz}), Poisson's ratios (ν_{yx} , ν_{yx} , ν_{xz} , ν_{zx} , ν_{yz} , ν_{zy}), and shear moduli (G_{xy} , G_{xz} , G_{yz}), where the subscripts denote the axes of planarity.

2.4 Finite element model

Engineering constants were then implemented in a FE model developed using LS-DYNA (Ansys inc.). The material configuration and corresponding FE model setup are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4. The model consisted of three primary parts: the impact striker and supports were modelled as rigid bodies using *MAT_RIGID* (MAT_020), while the specimen was defined using the *MAT_ENHANCED_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE* (MAT_054/055).

Boundary conditions were applied such that the impact striker motion was constrained to vertical translation (z-direction), replicating the actual experimental impact setup. The supports were fully

constrained in all degrees of freedom (translation and rotation in x , y , and z axes), while the specimen was simply supported with all degrees of freedom unrestrained. The impactor was given an initial velocity matching the experimental conditions, where the peak impact force was recorded for comparison with experimental results.

Figure 3: Material configuration: (a) SMC 10 mm tapes, (b) SMC 30 mm tapes, (c) UD carbon fiber

Figure 4: Finite element model for three-point bending impact

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Impact properties

The results of the three-point bending impact experiments are presented in Figure 5 and Figure 6. Both the impact strength and SEA increased as the tape length of SMC increased from 10 mm to 30 mm. This improvement is attributed to enhanced load transfer efficiency with longer tapes, which facilitate more effective stress transfer from the matrix to the fibers during impact, thereby increasing the overall energy absorption. In shorter tapes, the number of tape-ends per unit volume is higher, acting as stress concentrators and sites for crack initiation. In contrast, longer tapes are preferable for bridging cracks, promoting more progressive damage, and contributing to improved impact resistance and SEA.

In hybrid configurations, where UD carbon fiber was over-molded on either the lower or upper surfaces of the SMC, SEA increased while impact strength decreased relative to the SMC specimens with 30 mm tape lengths. Although the UD layer possesses superior in-plane properties compared to SMC, their off-axis properties are significantly lower, which limits their performance under flexural impact conditions present in the three-point bending impact test. Furthermore, UD materials tend to be more brittle than SMC, and are prone to delamination upon impact, which can serve as a stress concentrator and reduce impact strength.

Despite reduction in strength, delamination increases the range of failure mechanisms and facilitates more distributed energy dissipation over time, leading to increased overall energy absorbed per unit mass. This trade-off is a common phenomenon in hybrid structures, where maximizing energy absorption is of greater importance than peak load capacity. In automotive applications, where crashworthiness and passenger safety are prioritized, materials that fail in controlled, energy dissipating mechanisms are preferred over those that fail catastrophically at higher loads. This highlights a strategic

design consideration in which functional performance regarding safety takes precedence over peak strength alone.

Figure 5: Impact strengths

Figure 6: Specific energy absorption

Figure 7 presents the damaged specimens following the impact test. The SMC specimens exhibited a distinct failure pattern characterized by a straight-line fracture at the midpoint, with minimal signs of delamination. In contrast, the over-molded hybrid specimens showed extensive delamination, indicating a different failure mechanism influenced by the presence of the UD layer.

Figure 7: Damaged specimen: (a) SMC_10, (b) SMC_30, (c) Hybrid_L, and (d) Hybrid_U

3.2 Engineering constant estimation

To predict the engineering constants of the materials used in this study, multi-scale modelling was performed. The raw material data of carbon fiber and polyamide-6, along with their volume fraction and fiber morphology, were used as direct input parameters. The Young's moduli obtained from previous studies, were compared to check the validity of the model.

The predicted Young's moduli for SMC with 10 mm tapes, SMC with 30 mm tapes, and the UD carbon fiber were 33.9 GPa, 42.5 GPa, and 127.9 GPa respectively. The obtained engineering constants highly resembled material properties tested in previous studies, indicating that the model reliably correlates tested data with predicted outcome. The mean-field homogenization provides a simple and efficient method for estimating the bulk properties of composites as presented in Table 3-5. Additionally, since unknown engineering constants can be estimated using relatively few input parameters, this approach serves as a practical starting point for simulations in FE analysis.

Engineering constant	Type	Values
E_{xx}	Young's modulus	33.9 GPa
E_{yy}		33.5 GPa
E_{zz}		11.4 GPa
ν_{xy}	Poisson's ratio	0.31
ν_{yx}		0.32
ν_{xz}		0.39
ν_{zx}		0.13
ν_{yz}		0.39
ν_{zy}		0.13
G_{xy}	Shear modulus	12.9 GPa
G_{xz}		2.6 GPa
G_{yz}		2.6 GPa

Table 3: Predicted engineering constants for SMC with 10 mm tapes

Engineering constant	Type	Values
E_{xx}	Young's modulus	42.5 GPa
E_{yy}		42.5 GPa
E_{zz}		11.9 GPa
ν_{xy}	Poisson's ratio	0.32
ν_{yx}		0.32
ν_{xz}		0.37
ν_{zx}		0.10
ν_{yz}		0.37
ν_{zy}		0.10
G_{xy}	Shear modulus	16.1 GPa
G_{xz}		2.6 GPa
G_{yz}		2.6 GPa

Table 4: Predicted engineering constants for SMC with 30 mm tapes

Engineering constant	Type	Values
E_{xx}	Young's modulus	127.9 GPa
E_{yy}		10.2 GPa
E_{zz}		10.2 GPa
ν_{xy}	Poisson's ratio	0.28
ν_{yx}		0.02
ν_{xz}		0.28
ν_{zx}		0.02

ν_{yz}		0.58
ν_{zy}		0.58
G_{xy}		3.6 GPa
G_{xz}	Shear modulus	3.6 GPa
G_{yz}		3.2 GPa

Table 5: Predicted engineering constants for UD carbon fiber

3.3 Finite element analysis and correlation

The engineering constants obtained from multi-scale modelling were implemented as input parameters for the FE analysis. The FE model, as shown in Figure 7, illustrates the progress stress distribution in the specimen immediately after impact and up to just prior to failure.

Figure 8: Finite element model of SMC specimen

The analytical results were correlated with the experimentally measured impact strength of SMC specimens tested at an impact velocity of 2.0 m/s. Due to limitations in accurately modeling the delamination behavior between the SMC and over-molded UD carbon fiber layers, the hybrid configurations were excluded from the current FE analysis. Based on the simulation results, the SMC with 10 mm tapes exhibited a peak impact force of 1.61 kN, corresponding to a calculated strength of 892 MPa, while the SMC with 30 mm tapes reached peak force of 1.99 kN corresponding to 1,102 MPa. These predicted values showed good agreement with the experimental results, achieving accuracies of 87% and 98% respectively. The comparison of peak impact forces for both materials is illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Peak impact forces: (a) SMC_10, and (b) SMC_30

To accurately characterize the delamination behavior of the hybrid materials, material models capable of capturing interlaminar failure – such as cohesive zone elements or contact-based debonding models are required. However, implementing such models necessitates more rigorous experimental characterization of interlaminar properties, along with extensive material data to properly define the delamination behavior. These efforts, while beyond the scope of the current study, would be essential for advanced modelling of hybrid composite systems and are recommended for future work.

4 CONCLUSIONS

CFRTP-SMC offers distinct advantages in forming complex shapes, cost-effectiveness for large-scale production, and favorable mechanical properties. However, the influence of tape length and over-molding with UD carbon fiber on their impact behavior remains insufficiently understood. This study examined the impact properties of SMC with different tape lengths, and evaluated the effect of UD carbon fiber over-molding through three-point bending impact test, multi-scale model analysis for engineering constant estimation, and FE analysis to validate the experimental findings. The methodologies, key findings, and interpretations are discussed in detail. The principal conclusions are summarized as follows:

- Tape length effect: tape length was found to significantly influence the impact performance of SMCs. Increasing the tape length from 10 mm to 30 mm resulted in notable improvements in both impact strength and specific energy absorption. These enhancements were primarily attributed to improved load transfer efficiency and more effective stress transmission from the matrix to the fibers during impact.
- Effect of UD carbon fiber over-molding: the over-molding of UD carbon fiber introduced a performance trade-off. While delamination between the UD layer and SMC reduced the peak impact strength, it expanded the range of failure mechanisms and enhanced energy dissipation, leading to increased overall energy absorption.
- Multi-scale modelling: the mean-field homogenization approach used in the multi-scale model proved effective for estimating bulk material properties and unknown engineering constants with limited input data. This method served as a practical foundation for subsequent FE simulations.
- FE analysis validation: the FE analysis demonstrated good agreement with experimental results in predicting the impact strength of SMC with different tape lengths. Although hybrid materials were not modelled in this study due to limitations in characterizing interfacial delamination, future work incorporating cohesive zone models and interlaminar failure criteria is recommended.
- Design implications: the findings emphasize the critical role of tape length and highlight the potential of UD carbon fiber over-molding as a design strategy. When properly engineered, over-molding can enhance crashworthiness and energy absorption, offering significant benefits for passenger safety in automotive applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] Takahashi, J., & Ishikawa, T. (2013). *Current Japanese activity in CFRTP for industrial application*. In *Composites Week @ Leuven: Texcomp-11 Conference* (pp. 1–8)
- [2] European Commission, Directorate-General for Environment, Baron, Y., Kosińska-Terrade, I., & Loew, C. (2023). *Study to support the impact assessment for the review of Directive 2000/53/EC on end-of-life vehicles: Final report*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/855228>
- [3] Liu, C., Zhao, R., Li, Q., Yadav, R., Ferdowsi, M. R. G., Wang, Z., An, M., & Naebe, M. (2023). Surface engineering of carbon fiber via upcycling of waste gases generated during carbon fiber production: A sustainable approach towards high-performance composites. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 255, 110624. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2023.110624>
- [4] Wan, Y., & Takahashi, J. (2016). Tensile and compressive properties of chopped carbon fiber tapes reinforced thermoplastics with different fiber lengths and molding pressures. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 87, 271–281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2016.05.005>
- [5] Wan, Y., & Takahashi, J. (2016). Tensile properties and aspect ratio simulation of transversely isotropic discontinuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics. *Composites Science and Technology*, 137, 167–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2016.10.026>

- [6] Alves, M., & Pimenta, S. (2020). The influence of 3D microstructural features on the elastic behaviour of tow-based discontinuous composites. *Composite Structures*, 251, 112484. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.112484>
- [7] Alves, M., Martulli, L. M., Kerschbaum, M., Swolfs, Y., Lomov, S. V., & Pimenta, S. (2023). A 3D finite element stochastic framework for the failure of tow-based discontinuous composites. *Composites Science and Technology*, 232, 109846. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2022.109846>
- [8] Katsivalis, I., Persson, M., Johansen, M., Moreau, F., Kullgren, E., Norrby, M., Zenkert, D., Pimenta, S., & Asp, L. (2024). Strength analysis and failure prediction of thin tow-based discontinuous composites. *Composites Science and Technology*, 245, 110342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2023.110342>